

UDC 37.013.83

DOI: 10.15587/2519-4984.2020.208336

INFORMAL AESTHETIC AND PEDAGOGICAL EDUCATION OF ELDERLY PEOPLE: IN SEARCH OF THE SOLUTION OF THE PROBLEM OF SOCIAL ORPHANHOOD OF CHILDREN OF PRESCHOOL AGENCY AS A RESULT OF LABOR MIGRATION OF PARENTS

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У статті розглянуто можливості організації інформальної естетико-педагогічної освіти літніх людей у контексті пошуку шляхів пом'якшення проблеми соціального сирітства дітей дошкільного віку як наслідку трудової міграції батьків.

За результатами бліц-опитування у закладах дошкільної освіти м. Харкова, встановлено, що велику долю відповідальності за розвиток і виховання дітей у ситуації поширення явища трудової міграції в Україні взяли на себе старші члени родин та / або літні няні, доглядальниці, гувернантки, які, разом з цим, відчують певні труднощі через брак педагогічної мотивації, нових методичних знань щодо організації виховної діяльності з дітьми, вмінь застосовувати творчий підхід до розвитку особистості дитини; бракує мобільних освітніх програм, спрямованих на формування в людини старшого віку сучасних, актуальних у суспільстві трудових навичок.

Для подолання соціального сирітства дітей дошкільного віку як наслідку трудової міграції їхніх батьків розроблено освітянський проект «Кольоровий світ дитинства – досвідченими руками», спрямований на розвиток у людей старшого віку здатності піклуватися про наймолодших, розвиваючи їхню здібність до художнього мислення, творчості, сприяючи формуванню навичок у галузях малювання, колорознавства, практичної графіки, декоративного мистецтва та основ дизайну, вивчаючи разом з ними природу, оточуюче середовище як невичерпне джерело образотворчого мистецтва.

Програма підготовки літніх людей до організації художньо-естетичної діяльності дошкільників повністю адаптована до занять в «Університетах третього віку» або інших подібних структурах інформальної освіти дорослих й забезпечує підвищення педагогічного потенціалу людей старшого віку. У межах курсу розроблено варіативні види (малювання, різьблення по дереву, лозоплетіння, гончарство, квілінг тощо) і форми організації художньо-мистецьких занять й педагогічної освіти літніх людей, а також навчання слухачів і слухачок застосуванню отриманих художньо-творчих навичок у сфері фріланса й промоутинга власних професійних послуг. Проект розрахований на тривалий результат – систематичну організацію курсу інформальної естетико-педагогічної освіти літніх людей як важливого шляху пом'якшення проблеми соціального сирітства дітей дошкільного віку як наслідку трудової міграції батьків

Ключові слова: інформальна освіта, естетико-педагогічні знання, літні люди, дошкільники, трудова міграція батьків

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1. Introduction

Today, the ideas of lifelong learning are especially relevant in Ukraine both due to their potential to retain labor resources in the country and given the undeniable practical benefits for preventing the negative consequences of the existing problem of labor migration in Ukraine. Labor migration – the movement of persons for the purpose of temporary employment, accompanied by crossing the border (external labor migration) or the boundaries of administrative units of Ukraine (internal migration) – has become today one of the most acute problems of local demographics.

According to demographers, by 2026 the population of Ukraine will decrease to 37 million, and about 27 % of them will be 60 years old and older [1]. Moreover, it should be emphasized, that among the most influ-

ential factors in the population decline, along with declining birth rates – the outflow of able-bodied youth abroad. According to the UN Office in Ukraine, every fifth Ukrainian is a potential migrant and would like to leave the village where he/she lives [2]. This causes a significant percentage increase among the population of Ukraine in the number of people, who have reached the retirement age, which, according to the Institute of Gerontology, has already reached the ratio – 231 retirees per 1,000 Ukrainians [3]. According to the optimistic scenario, in the near future in Ukraine there will be about 4 million young people; according to the pessimistic – only 2.8 million [4].

Accordingly, the labor force of Ukraine will consist of older people, whose efficiency in modern working conditions remains minimal. N. Prokopenko, an employ-

ee of the Institute of Gerontology of Ukraine, emphasizes that the active work of the elderly is one of the main guarantees of their health and interest in life, and the vast majority of these people want to work, although decent employment in Ukraine today is almost unattainable, because they are rejected by the society as a potential labor resource, instead they are offered social ageing [3]. According to the national researcher Y. Lysenko, in the new information society, older people become alienated and marginalized even singled out in the group, due to the lack of resource adaptation in a changing society [5].

Paradoxically, along with the state's restrictions on the access of this age group to employment, according to official data, people of both sexes under the age of 70 are included in the economically active population, which provides labor supply in the labor market, which is possible by the new flexible phenomenon of working people. Thus, in particular, an employed person is considered to be a person, who works at least one hour for hire for remuneration in cash or in kind, individually (independently), in individual citizens or in his/her own (family) enterprise; works for free at an enterprise, in his/her own business, which belongs to any of the members of the household, or in a private company in order to sell products, produced as a result of this activity, etc. [1]. However, although theoretically the availability of different types of variable employment for older people has increased, in fact the change in priorities for competitive specialties in the labor market has reduced the opportunities for such people to get jobs and narrowed the range of employment, available to them.

Referring to the statement of Yu. Lysenko, we emphasize that the dynamics of socialization, including labor, of the elderly is closely linked to their social status, society's attitude to them, the roles and functions, assigned to them by the community, customs, norms and traditions of a nation [5]. Traditionally in Ukraine, caring for the younger generation, passing on wisdom and social experience, and preserving the national identity of Ukrainians was considered a natural pastime for the elderly. And although today there is no denying the need to attract skilled labor to innovative areas of work (blogging, copywriting, network marketing, freelance, modeling business, etc.), where they can achieve significant success, we emphasize the need to maintain and develop traditional types of work activities of elderly Ukrainians (raising children, arts, crafts, etc.). This will help increase the pedagogical potential of the Ukrainian society in the context of growing problems of social orphanhood of children, including as a result of labor migration of parents.

Given the above, we believe that the way out of this situation is the development of various forms of non-formal adult education, which would expand the range of work skills throughout life via the implementation of mobile educational programs, aimed at providing older people modern, relevant in society and, together with this, natural and culturally appropriate work skills. One of our suggested initiatives for the development and testing of such structures is the educational project "Colourful World of Childhood - experienced hands," directed ground for aesthetic development of older people, improving their ability to care for younger, developing their creative skills in the fields of colour science, painting,

decorative arts, design, studying with them nature, the environment as an inexhaustible source of fine arts; contributing to the growth of the level of spirituality and the formation of aesthetic culture, the development of aesthetic and emotional attitude to works of decorative art and design, the ability to understand and appreciate folk art; education of an active attitude to the aesthetic phenomena of reality and art; purposeful and systematized formation of practical skills of artistic and creative activity.

This will practically solve the problem of replenishing the working life of the state through encouragement of the new, popular in the community activities of populations, traditionally subject to labor marginalization – older people, who develop their work activity, acquiring new skills, fostering a creative look at the world around. New employment opportunities for elderly are to help prevent the spread of the consequences of child abandonment as a result of migration of parents-workers to provide family education and care for children, stimulate their creativity, adding the best examples of national culture and handicrafts.

2. Literary review

Analyzing the previous experience of scientific and practical development issues of formal education of older people, particularly in the context of overcoming the negative effects of migration, should be primarily in the widespread practice in the organization "Universities of the Third Age." This, until recently, innovative educational practice is currently focused on the formation of knowledge among Ukrainian retirees that will not only be able to bring them pleasure, but also provide practical benefits. For example, mastering the classroom "University" basics of computer literacy, seniors will be able to monitor their own Internet page stories, charges to the pension fund, etc. [3].

Today, "Universities of the Third Age" operate in many regions of Ukraine. This is due to the fact that the state has begun to pay more attention to the problems of the elderly. After all, if a full-fledged life abroad is just beginning after retirement, in Ukraine after receiving a pension certificate you can get into social isolation. This form of education may be an important starter of the platform to implement a new educational project "Colourful World of Childhood - experienced hands" that expands employment opportunities of older people, increases connections between generations, increases the pedagogical potential of community work in the increasing migration in Ukraine.

It should be noted, that the problems of the elderly and the possibility of their involvement in education and work and after work, in particular by means of art, are quite well studied in foreign theory and practice.

Elderly education as a progressive idea has been relevant in Europe since the 1970s. At the practical level, this idea was first implemented by the professor of Toulouse university (Université de Toulouse, France), Pierre Vellas (Pie re Vellas). In the summer of 1972 the first in recorded history Painting for the elderly was implemented, and a result of which is the apparent conclusion is that it is culture and art that serve the most powerful means of restoring vital resources of the individual, lost

with age [6]. Thus, the art began to be seen also as an important source of inspiration for those, who despite age are striving for the manifestation of creative activity, new knowledge [7].

The idea of seniors Education quickly spread in Europe and appeared to support the need for this kind of education at the international level. The central coordinating body, providing this support, began in 1977 among the people at the Association of Universities of the Third Age (Association Internationale des Universités de Trisième Age – AIUTA). For the non-discriminatory designation of people of this age group, the term "third age" actually appeared which from that time began to be actively used to denote the elderly [8]. The main task of AIUTA is proclaimed in the charter of this organization: "to unite all over the world universities of the third age and organizations that have other names, but the same tasks"; the main principle of the association is "the creation with the support of universities around the world of an international network of life education, with the aim of research and with the help and participation of the elderly in their educational needs" [9].

In modern international practice, the concept of Universities of the Third Age is associated with the international movement, which aims to stimulate community older members to active life and self-fulfillment through the creation and functioning of educational and recreational facilities of diverse type and nature of activity [10].

Note that the idea of establishing such institutions Nabeul and distribution had been born in French-speaking territories (France, Belgium, Switzerland, Quebec), and over time, this experience spread in Europe, governmental and Scandinavian countries (Italy, Spain, Poland, Sweden and Finland). In English-speaking territories (Great Britain, Australia, New Zealand, Malta and Cyprus), such "Universities" began to be established in the 80's of the twentieth century.

In different countries, while maintaining the general direction and principles of informal education of the elderly, there are differences in the organization of their education. For example, in the United Kingdom, universities of the third age are independent institutions, informal associations of various structures, consisting of groups of people, who have volunteered to share their knowledge, skills, abilities and experience. They are also called the only national educational organization, which is managed by its members [11]. The tradition of such activities was started in 1982 by Peter Leslett, Michael Young and Eric Midwinter, who tried to facilitate access to education for the elderly, as well as to involve them in the organization of the educational process, based on their activity, talents, experience [12]. In 2014, 240 Universities of the Third Age, which worked with 527 interest groups, which enrolled 131,200 students and trainees, have been officially registered in the UK. Now the network "Universities" expanded to 1010, and in their composition, there are 385,029 people [13]. Note that in the UK it is also the extremely common form of distance learning, focused on improving an educational level of elderly people [14–16].

The essential features of the universities of the third age is that joining them does not require the profes-

sional training and professional experience, does not set strict examination barriers that are difficult to overcome by older students. At the same time, Kali Lightfood describes the experience of teaching third- year students in the United States, where they, despite the lack of usual academic requirements and strict control, feel a great responsibility for their own education [17].

More close to the Ukraine as geographically and by historical roots, in the Czech Republic "University one third of the third age" was launched in 80 years of the twentieth century [18], and despite some difficult socio political circumstances of the last century, the elderly are always focused on quality and compliance with Euro level [19]. In the 90s of the twentieth century with number of objects that provide such education, "universities of the third age", included in the system of higher education, expanded their branch. Accordingly, the "university of the third age" began to be considered as an educational service, aimed at the elderly, but carried out exclusively within a higher education institution (university), which is primarily a guarantee of the quality of education. Thus, in the Czech Republic Seniors education was a component of the higher education system. Elderly people are gradually beginning perceived by society as people, who are active and who do not stop the development educational pulses for updating their knowledge, skills and experience.

Various means have been accumulated in the Czech experience to stimulate such activity. In Charles University (Prague), for example, music education is an important factor of the development of a personality. The course of musical topography of the Czech Republic is aimed at the development of the personality of the elderly and at satisfying their interests and desires [20].

In the Republic of Poland, the education of the elderly is less formalized. Its main focus is "Clubs Senyora" – a rather popular group, organizing the elderly, the meeting place, which organizes classes and activities on the needs of this category of persons. Their main function is socialization of the elderly, stimulating their activity and providing contact with the culture [21]. "Clubs Senyora", unlike other forms of social security, are most popular among the elderly. Such a club is a centre that deals with the development of cultural, educational, social and recreational life of the elderly. Participation in such a club is a great opportunity for active recreation, development of hobbies and passions, as well as gaining new sensations and experiences. The facilitators of this institution make efforts to adapt the training offers to the needs and interests of the interested members. In addition to cultural and artistic and educational function, "Clubs Senyora" often function as aid, taking on the challenge to help most needy, sick and lonely members. The main objectives of that is to ensure appropriate conditions for a pleasant and useful leisure of elderly, to meet their own interests, to support and also strengthen social contacts, sociability [22].

Although all appointed organization models and practices of elderly education are effective, in Ukraine there is a need in summarizing the experience gained and the creation of a new system of elderly education, aimed at cultural development, improving the ability of older people to take care of the youngest, transferring their

desire for creativity, contributing to the formation of skills in the fields of drawing, colour, practical graphics, decorative arts; contributing to the growth of the level of spirituality and the formation of aesthetic culture, the development of aesthetic and emotional attitude to works of decorative art and design, the ability to understand and appreciate folk art; education of an active attitude to the aesthetic phenomena of reality and art; purposeful and systematized formation of practical skills of artistic and creative activity.

This will practically solve the problem of replenishing the working life of the state through encouragement the new, popular in the community activities of populations, traditionally subject to labor marginalization – older people, who develop their work activity, acquiring new skills, fostering a creative look at the world around. New employment opportunities for the elderly will help prevent the spread of social orphanhood as a result of labor migration of working parents, provide family upbringing and care for children, stimulate their creativity, attach to the best examples of national culture and crafts, educate the community and society.

The problem of labor migration as a factor in changing the dynamics of the pedagogical influence of the family on children has been studied in foreign intelligence, mainly in terms of studying the gender asymmetry of migration processes. Yes, scientists [23, 24] consider temporary employment of men abroad in an atypical field of work at home as a positive factor in increasing parental potential and development of the institution of fatherhood, seeing such employment as a powerful way to involve men in usually inconspicuous, unpaid homework and care of children of preschool age, dominated by women. Although in general, the removal of the father from the family, as a result of long-term labor migration, is perceived as a destructive factor for this social institution.

Adverse enough of a factor that negatively affects the education of preschool children in Ukraine, where it is traditionally seen as a female thing, is that the proportion of women in the total number of international migrants is steadily growing. In 2000 women accounted for about 51 % of migration in developed countries and almost 46 % of migration in developing regions, which include Ukraine [25]. Considering the two main regions of destination of Ukrainian migrant workers, it becomes obvious that men earn, on average, 22 % more in the CIS countries, while in the EU there is equality between personal incomes of men and women. However, according to estimates of the International Organization for Migration in Ukraine, this situation is contrary to the proportion of female migrants with higher education that is much higher (53 %), comparing with male migrant workers, who have the same level of education (37 %) [26].

Migration streams of women are structurally investigated based on the identification of socio-cultural features of perception of women in society (for example, Mexicans in the US and Paraguayans in Argentina) [27]. The subject of research among foreign scholars were the issues of causal links of female migration, its trends, areas of employment of migrant women, opportunities for their economic activity by ethnicity in the destination country [28–30].

The research has found that long-term migrant labor of mostly widowed or divorced women (29 % of migrants compared to 10% of migrants, respectively) allows them to earn and thus be self-sufficient. On the other hand, married migrants in most cases, migrated with their husbands (58 % of women compared with only 27 % of married men) [26]. Women who are bringing up one or more children of preschool age, and women who do not have children, even under adverse conditions in employment receive higher incomes due to longer working hours, at the same time, domestic realities, perception of family duties by women cause reduction in the intensity of their work, and, accordingly, the possibility of earnings [28].

There are also older people among migrants, although according to the research, the majority of short-term (64 %) and long – term (71 %) migrant workers are between the ages of 18 and 44. Older people, mostly women (47 % of women / 28 % of men), are more prone to short-term labor migration. The predominance of women in the older age group is explained by the demand for labor abroad. The country's female migrant workers (43 %) tend to work in the household and agricultural sectors. These sectors work mainly attract older women (64 % of the age group of 45–65 years compared to about 12 % of the age group of 18–29 years) [26]. In terms of age, the probability of return is directly proportional to the age of migrant workers: the older the migrant, the more likely he / she is to return home. This conclusion makes sense because older migrant workers are more likely to have achieved their primary migration goals; or other factors motivate them to return home, such as health problems or inability to adapt to changing labor market conditions in destination countries [26].

Based on the analysis of existing world and domestic experience and the results of discussions by the international scientific community on issues, related to the problem, raised in our study, we can say that the idea of continuing education of older people as a potential pedagogical resource is relevant and productive today. The development and implementation of various forms of such education can mitigate the effects of labor migration in Ukraine. Novelty and practical significance of this study is related to the development of new methodological concept of education – educational project "Colourful World of Childhood – experienced hands" for the elderly, which ensures the maintenance of labor resources in Ukraine and attraction to different areas of professional activity (upbringing of children, arts and crafts, folk crafts, etc.), which will increase the pedagogical potential of the Ukrainian society in the face of growing problems of social orphanhood as a result of labor migration of parents.

3. The aim and objectives of the study

The aim of the study was to substantiate and investigate the development project of elderly informal education "Colourful World of Childhood – experienced hands," which is to provide the increasing educational potential of the Ukrainian society, given the growing problem of child abandonment, particularly as a result of migration of parents.

To achieve this aim, the following objectives were set:

1. To investigate the state of labor migration in Ukraine and the world, as well as foreign and domestic experience in solving socio-economic and psychological problems of the elderly and the possibility of their involvement in education and labor and post-employment activities, including art, as an important resource for mitigation of consequences of labor migration due to the strengthening of the pedagogical potential of society in the direction of solving the problem of social orphanhood of preschool children.

2. The blitz polls were organized with students in preschool education establishments in Kharkiv to show the real state of the problem of educational neglect and abandonment of preschool children and the role of older people as a potentially important factor of compensation for the lack of proper parental influence on children.

3. To create a program for training older people as customized to employment in the "University of the Third Age" or other similar information structures of adult education to organize artistic activity and ECT for preschoolers, called "Colour world of childhood – experienced hands".

4. To develop divergent types (drawing, art carving, pottery, making national toys, quilling, decorative painting, decoupage, making artificial flowers, embroidery, Easter egg) and forms (training, workshop, practice, exchange of experience, discussion) of organization of art classes and teacher education of elderly in order to prepare them to care for preschool children, to teach students and to develop their creative skills in freelancing and promoting their professional services.

5. To involve partner organizations to the program training of older people to organize preschool activities in "Colour world of childhood – experienced hands".

4. Materials and methods

The study used theoretical methods – analysis, generalization of information on socio-economic and psychological problems of the elderly and the possibility of their involvement in education and labor and post-employment activities; modeling, designing the structure of non-formal education of older people "Colourful world of childhood – experienced hands", forecasting the results of its implementation as an important factor in mitigating the effects of labor migration through strengthening the pedagogical potential of society to deal with social orphanhood of preschool children, as well as empirical methods: observation, questionnaire, survey of educators, parents and relatives of children in preschool education institutions of Kharkiv .

The research was performed at the Faculty of Early Childhood Education Kharkiv National Pedagogical University, named after G. C. Skovoroda in 2017 – 2019. It was attended by 27 student interns, who interviewed 75 parents and other relatives of preschool children, 32 educators of preschool education in Kharkiv, who acted as bases for student practice.

The program of preparation of elderly people for the organization of artistic and aesthetic activities of preschoolers is focused on the course of 20 elderly people, interested in improving the readiness for aesthetic educa-

tion of preschool children, and adapted to classes at "Universities of the Third Age" or other similar adult information education. It is planned to involve territorial centers of social service of citizens and public organizations of Kharkiv in the implementation of the program.

5. Results and discussion

In September 2019 lecturers of the preschool teacher faculty and department of the theory and technology of pre-school education and artistic disciplines of Kharkiv National Pedagogical University began to develop a course for people, who could work towards solving the urgent problems in society, connected with children of preschool age, who were left without proper parental care as a result of labor migration of parents. The idea of the course appeared as a result of practical observations in preschool institutions of Kharkiv. Thus, passing practice in preschool education, future teachers each year increasingly began to tick "loose age" and significant spread of such negative social phenomena as deviant and even criminal behaviour of children, bullying, various manifestations of dependent behaviour in preschool children etc. As a rule, such problems of preschool children were associated with child neglect, reduced quality of pedagogical influence of the family on them, due to increased professional activity of parents, the need to earn for the family, full use of their potential in the labor process, which required distancing from the family and children, often going abroad.

Young students conducted a mini research in preschool education in Kharkiv, which was revealed today, along with the previously known causes of educational neglect of children of preschool age – unemployment, alcohol and drug addiction of parents, destruction of family structures. The antisocial way of life of a family is the leading position as a factor of child neglect, employment and labor migration of parents. It mostly and usually means to work abroad; today women's labor migration is more common.

It is also concluded, correlated with assessments of scientists [25], according to which the traditional understanding of migration as a predominantly male occupation has changed and women become independent entities, which are involved in the migration process as well as men. There is even a separate term for them – "unattached migrants" – independent of the movement of a husband or family. This, of course, caused a significant elimination of women as agents of pedagogical influence of the family on children, which was recorded in our study.

In the course of observation and conversations with children, parents and their substitutes, educators, it was found, that a large share of responsibility for the development and upbringing of children in this situation was assumed by older family members (grandparents) and / or the elderly: nannies, caregivers, governesses. It was also established, that these individuals are experiencing difficulties in caring for their students and pupils, including not only an increase of physical load, caused by the daily business of child care, but, above all, lack of teacher motivation, lack of new interesting information for the child, modern methodological knowledge on the organization of educational activities with children, the

ability to apply a creative approach to the development of the child's personality, etc.

The courses for informative system for adults "coloured world of childhood - experienced hands", directly aimed at improving the educational potential of older people, developing their possibilities at art with children of preschool age, handing them the ability to artistic thinking, creative approach to the perception of the world around, skills in the fields of art, the ability to understand and appreciate folk art, purposeful and systematic formation of love and respect for native culture, were designed.

The course covers a fairly wide range of artistic knowledge and artistic and creative activities. Thus, students must learn the basic laws of construction of decorative forms in art, get acquainted with the types of arts and crafts, their history, morphology, means of expression and technology of decorative products, master artistic and creative techniques (drawing, wood carving, basket weaving, pottery making national toys, quilling, decorative painting, decoupage, making artificial flowers, embroidery, egg painting) integrate a conscious approach to the use of colour in various fields of human activity art and design, the basic techniques of colours that match with demands of general artistic development, special issues in fine arts. At the same time, much attention in the content of the program is paid to the discovery of art as a factor in promoting social integration of a child, harmonization of its internal state, encouragement of positive creative activity, psychological features of aesthetic development of preschool children, mastering systems and methods of organizing classes for preschool children with the help of new art techniques. In addition, within each topic, each class, the object of the study is methods and technical self-management to promote their services on the labor market, cooperation with employers and partners.

The tasks for the course for elderly people are:

- development of personal integrity, spirituality and formation of aesthetic culture, education of listeners' initiative, independence, desire for creativity, mastering aesthetic and emotional attitude to works of art and design, the ability to understand and appreciate folk art;

- education of the active attitude to aesthetic phenomena of reality and art, actualization of the creative potential and development of creative self-realization in various types of artistic creativity, decorative art and design;

- development of artistic perception: the ability to feel the colour, shape, awareness of the emotional expressiveness of the object, to select the means to convey its figurative content, the acquisition of basic knowledge of colour;

- study of the basics of the physical nature of light and colour, physiological foundations of colour vision, psychology of colour perception, study and practical mastering of the basic laws of colour harmony and construction of colour compositions, development of students' sense of colour and colour harmony;

- development of spatial thinking, education of sense of form, composition, integrity of vision; formation of skills of short-term sketch, pictures and images from nature, observation of nature, accumulation of artistic impressions about it;

- mastering the basics of knowledge in the field of colour science by students, mastering the skills of applying this knowledge in solving practical problems in painting, artistic design, industrial graphics, interior;

- purposeful and systematic formation of practical skills for artistic and creative activities, development of skills of analysis of phenomena, objects, landscape details both separately and in interaction with the surrounding objects, lighting, environment, preparation for the creation of decorative arts and design ;

- understanding of artistic relations shaped a head tribute to the work of the idea and content for mastering the system of methodological tools, which ensured the success of the educational process in the classroom for preschool children;

- formation of practical skills of work with colour in painting; disclosure of individual psychological features of colour of works of art, the specifics of colour of children's art and the role of colour in the formation of national culture;

- students' mastering of technological methods of processing various materials, equipping with necessary practical skills and abilities of manufacturing and art design of products, preparation of the future specialist for creation of subjects of arts and crafts and design, application of the acquired knowledge, abilities and skills at performance of creative tasks, education and upbringing of children;

- providing knowledge about the peculiarities of preschool age, psychological and pedagogical features of aesthetic perception of preschoolers, methods and types of art classes with preschool children at home and outdoors, etc.

The training of students and trainees within the educational project "Colourful World of Childhood – experienced hands" consists of five modules (150 hours), each designed for one credit (30 hours that will be included are: 18 hours of group classes with coaches, 6 hours – distance learning and 6 hours – independent work to perform a credit creative task). The cycles have the following names: "Colour Science", "Fundamentals of Compositional Literacy", "Drawing and Plein air Workshop", "Decorative Art and Fundamentals of Design", "Methods of teaching art to preschool children".

During the course of mastering the first module – "Colour Science" – older listeners are able to retrieve tons and knowledge of the properties of colour and light; terminology of colour science; basic patterns of colour perception; determination of the main characteristics of colour; basic laws of psychophysiological perception of colour; techniques of coloristics and principles of colour harmony; rules are the modes of colours and colour combinations (contrasts, nuances); colour mixing (optical, mechanical and spatial); spatial objective and subjective colour quality; features of national symbolism of colour (in Ukrainian art); basics of creative collaboration with preschool children.

Mastering the themes of this module also provides the acquisition of skills to create a colour palette with specified characteristics; use samples of natural colour harmonies when creating compositions; take into account the associative and optical properties of colour in shaping, painting and decorative compositions; to create as-

sociative-figurative compositions, harmoniously coordinated in colour, on the set themes; apply artistically expressive means of colour and symbolic properties of colour in creative and design activities; encourage preschoolers to make and implement design decisions.

Individuals, involved in listening to the second module of the course – "Decorative Arts and Fundamentals of Design", – should learn the basic principles of artistic and decorative activities; methods of artistic and decorative design of products; methods of teaching decorative art to preschool children.

In the process of mastering this module, the elderly acquire the ability to use the gained artistic and creative knowledge for artistic and decorative design of various products; feel the colour, shape, be aware of the emotional expressiveness of the object; to carry out selection of the means, allowing to transfer its figurative maintenance; have the technology of processing various materials; comprehensively solve artistic and decorative, structural and technological problems; apply the method of teaching decorative arts to preschool children.

The third module educational course for seniors – "Drawing and plein air workshop" – provides using their knowledge of the specifics of drawing at nature; expedient work techniques that increase the creative level of the artist; existing difficulties that complicate the work with nature, the diversity, the variety of shapes, sizes, constant changes in lighting, depending on the weather and the seasons.

Practically studying the drawing and going through workshop, students of the course acquire skills that will help in working with preschool children to understand the artistic impressions of what they saw, find the most interesting, most important, select the necessary details and conquer them as a whole; learn to figure and convey hundred of distinct lightings, atmospheric effects, a sense of space that constantly changes the status and mood of nature, to depict an architectural object in its most characteristic condition, the surrounding architectural landscape, given the linear and aerial perspective in various periods of time; learn the ability to explain the basic techniques of creating a picture to a preschool child, to teach the techniques for capturing instantaneous states of nature.

The fourth module – "Fundamentals of compositional literacy" – provides students with knowledge of the basic laws of techniques and means of composition; methods of division by "golden section"; various methods of constructing balanced formal compositions; algorithm in the construction of subject-spatial composition; features of poster art.

The skills, acquired by older people at mastering this module, are not limited to the ability to choose the appropriate techniques and means of formal composition and build subject-spatial composition, they teach to be creative in the transfer of artistic means of certain psychological states; teach to formalize the language of visual information of the work, possession of artistically expressive means of performing compositions; learn to create posters in the social direction and pass on the acquired knowledge and skills to children.

After mastering the topics of the fifth module – "Methods of teaching art to preschool children" - the

elderly must learn the technology of manual and mechanical processing of various materials, the basic principles of artistic and decorative activities, methods of design and decoration of products, methods of teaching artistic work to preschool children. They learn to use the acquired knowledge for artistic and decorative design of products; acquire the ability to feel the color, shape, awareness of the emotional expressiveness of the object; to select materials and means that allow to convey its figurative content; have the technology of processing various materials; comprehensively solve artistic and decorative, structural and technological problems; to apply the method of teaching artistic work to preschool children.

The module "Color Science" provides for the mastery of several complex thematic blocks.

First – Light and color – begins on information for disclosure of topics and 1.1 "Nature of light and color" considers light, color and comparison between the colors of the pigment (paints), the main characteristics of color (color tone, brightness, saturation), optic, mechanical, spatial mixing of colors and methods of mixing paints. It expands knowledge of the participants on the range of sciences, studying color (chemistry, biology, medicine, etc.), color and modern, colorful look at the phenomenon of culture, information and communication technologies in color. Problems in pedagogy and graphic design, age features of colour feeling formation, philosophical and basic knowledge, influence on color aesthetic is the education of children, development of associative and imaginative thinking, emotional color sensitivity detection of individual study of color. In practice (in the form of master classes, workshops) the following topics will be under consideration. Topic 1.2. – "Spectrum" – aims to address questions regarding the merits and principles in colour. Topic 1.3. – "Isochromy" – provides a study of its composition in one color spot, tone. Topic 1.4. – "Contrast and nuance" – understanding the interaction of its objects in the composition. Topic 1.5. – "Merchromy" – mastering the basics for composition where colors are subordinated to one forged main color.

The long thematic block is called "Psychology of color" and is directly aimed at listeners' mastering of aesthetic and therapeutic color techniques in working with preschool children.

Within topic 2.1. – "Features of psychological influence of color on people" – in practical forms – color psychology and human physiological functions. While mastering topic 2.2. – "Color in the composition of the picture" – theoretical consideration of concept creation of color harmonies; for classification of colored harmonies; systematization and construction principles of known colored systems and methods of selecting harmonious color combinations for these systems (O. Runge system V.Ostvalda, theories of V. Kandinsky, P. Klyee, J. Itten and etc.). Also within this subject the phenomenon of form an efficient innovation infrastructure and abstract compositions is showed.

Within topic 2.3. – "Functions of color in nature" – the issues of color in conjunction with objects and phenomena are linked. Topic 2.4. – "Spectrum Symbolism of colors" – dedicated color national culture of arts and crafts from different countries and eras. Within its limits

color associations, color syncretism, color analytical characteristics of ancient and modern paintings (art-associative compositions and abstract painting) are also considered.

The second module is called "Fundamentals of compositional literacy", within which the compositional laws, principles, means and techniques are covered. In particular topic 1.1., the law of equilibrium, the laws of unity and subordination are considered; it highlights the concept, organizing the second component of the artwork, mass of the composition, organization of the compositional center. Topic 1.2. – "Contrast, nuance identity" – touches contrasting, nuancing and identical in art as a means of a harmony.

While mastering topic 1.3. – "The basic proportions, arithmetic, geometric, harmonic, golden section" – students and trainees are taught methods in harmonization and use of composition. Within topic 1.4. – "Types of composition: Frontal. Deep-spatial" – they learn the techniques of placement in one plane of the elements of form in two directions – vertical and horizontal – in relation to the viewer, consider the composition as having a closed surface that is perceived from all sides; learn the peculiarities of the structure of deep-spatial composition.

In addition, the module "Fundamentals of composition literacy" shows elderly forming representations of formal and subject-dimensional in compositions. Specifically, within topic 2.1. – "Formal composition. Golden Section" – participants are instilled the idea of integrity, subordination of the secondary to the main (the presence of a dominant), the balance of the artistic composition, its focus on the golden section – harmonious in proportion .

Topic 2.2. – "Analysis of golden section in pictures " – provides elderly people with perceptions and appearances in the sense of beauty and harmony. Topic 2.3. – "Compositional techniques and schemes of still life construction " – provides knowledge about the compositional center, the principles of expressiveness of the image: shape, material, texture, color, as well as typical schemes of still life construction. According to the content of topic 2.4. – "Specifics and features of composition in decorative art " – students study the factors that play a significant role in the composition of a work of art in decorative art.

The third module "Plein air painting workshop", provides older kindergarten teachers with the weapons as knowledge, skills and with respect to Picture of nature, including flora . Thus, within topic 1.1. – "Drawing branches, trees, flowers and other elements of the plant world " – they learn plants, different by the plastic and form, placing the image. We study the structures in the figure, for example, the structure of the branch, the proportional ratio of its parts, and the plastic motion of the form. Develop the spatial arrangement of parts of the drawing and its planning. Techniques and plant various graphic materials. Topic 1.2. – "Drawing landscape " – contains questions about searching subjects with typical features, composition image identifying of heaven and earth. Topic 1.3 is important – "Picture figures of human in the open air " – because it provides elderly with figures of a man, different by the plastic and form. The picture "I'm single figures and groups" shows differences in figures and planned character, various materials of the human figure.

Within the module "Painting and Plein air Workshop" there is a practical consolidation of skills in the image of the object in the natural environment .Topic 2.1. – "Picture of architectural object " – contains a motive picture of characteristic features, opens opportunities for a true image, identifying key relations between sky, land and buildings, providing skills to claim constructions and buildings, basic tonal relations, means the volume of light and shade, etc.

Topic 2.2. – "Drawing of people in the open air" – involves a practical choice of different plastic and shape of figures and types of people; the picture I'm single figures and groups; various graphic materials of the person presentation, type, portrait. Topic 2.3. – "Drawing birds and animals in the open air" – provides practical working skills in different plastic forms of figures of animals, birds; the place of a figure and groups in an image; location and planned figures of art and, transfer of figures of animals and birds by various graphic materials; creation of an animal in the form of an animal with a generalized transfer of volume and lighting.

Note that the module "painting and plein air workshop" is aimed, in particular, to instilling participants skills of various methods we perform pictures (paint brush large spots, in the wet , etc.) and all techniques in drawing with a pencil, coal, pen, ink, brush, pastel, etc .

The fourth module "Decorative art and design fundamentals" involves consideration of the type of art as a component of visual activities. Topic 1.1. opens with a structure and kind of arts and crafts, and characteristics (types, genres). Topic 1.3. covers the principles, approaches, forms and methods of acquainting preschool children with decorative and applied arts, and teaching of decorative drawing, modeling, applications.

During the study course it is planned to disclose a law of arts and crafts, traditional art and integral art, tectonics. Thus, topic 2.1 is devoted to the explanation of the content of the main laws of decorative and applied arts. In studying topic 2.2. the theory and practice of creation at decorative and applied art are mastered, their variants are considered. Topic 2.3. – is devoted to the study of its application as the main direction of decorative and applied art. Topic 2.4. – "Collage, paper and origami – as modern types of decorative creative works".

Pertykivsky and Slobozhansky paintings are studied within the framework of theme 2.5, and theme 2.6 is devoted to the production of planar and three-dimensional floral compositions.

Special attention within the rest of this module is given to practical listeners' mastering of reception and means along with arts and crafts: first toys, dishes, Easter eggs; children's books; mastering the techniques of plane and three-dimensional decoupage. In addition, students develop skills of creating an aesthetic and educational environment, in particular, design of children's rooms.

The last module of the course – "Methods of teaching art work of preschool age children", called for assimilation of bases for art and constructive activity of children. Topic 1.1. – "The essence of artistic work at the modern stages of preschool education" provided a brief historical outline of the development of artistic handicrafts, its importance in education of preschool children;

requirements for notions of artistic work; disclosure of the knowledge, skills and abilities that children acquire in art classes, for their further work and artistic and aesthetic activities.

Topic 1.2 – "Working with paper and cardboard" – is devoted to the formation of skills in the manufacture of planar products. Participants are provided with brief information about the production and use of paper, cardboard in the work: whatman, velvet, wrapping, fluorescent paper; soft, pearl, metallized paperboard etc. The constructive and decorative features of various paper and cardboard are studied; tools and devices, used in the manufacture of paper and cardboard: scissors (appropriate to the size of a child's hand), stationery knife, awl (only educator work them), needle, thread, glue brush, pencils, markers, ruler, their purpose and storage.

Decorative design is practically mastered in the manufacture of applications (breaking, symmetrical, plot and paper plastic) by cutting, combining and gluing.

Topic 1.3. – "Manufacture of three-dimensional products" – provides the study of elderly educators in the basics of designing toys from the main pattern (a square divided into 16 parts); different directions of a paper rectangle and a square for the manufacture of bulk toys; design of three-dimensional products, made of a sheet of paper, folded in different directions, and cardboard with a cut along the fold line and with cutting off a part of the main pattern. It is almost perfected ability of the first processing of a surface and edge of the bulk product, variants of manufacturing of the basic pattern.

Within six course modules the basics, the natural materials, as well as work with fabric and with other artificial material, are studied. Topic 2.1. – "Production of flat floral compositions" – the study included stocking of leaves, flowers, straw, shells; processing, storage and preparation work. We considered also building and supplies for natural materials: scissors, brush.

Highlighted issues, considered warm, cold, related colors. Techniques in the use of color, texture and structure of leaves, straws, flowers in creating decorative compositions, the concept of "report", "compositional scheme", in particular, the compositional schemes of placement of decor in a given format (square, rectangle, circle, oval, etc.) were studied. The techniques of creating a subject, plot and plot-thematic compositions, observance of color harmony, unity of style, checking the completion of work were practically mastered with the listeners.

Topic 2.2. – "Production of three-dimensional floral compositions" contains questions: constructive and decorative properties of various natural materials; from the means of procurement of natural materials to a technology of their processing; preparation of materials for the work; main materials and accessories to make metal floral compositions (scissors, knife, needle, crayons, paint, glue), auxiliary materials: paper, wire, thread, oasis, semolina, sand.

Topic 2.3. – "Working with eggshell" – is dedicated to the organization of work with eggshell (toy, mosaic "Crackle"). Methods of preparation of eggs for the work, blowing technology are covered; auxiliary materials: colored cardboard and paper, plastic, glue, plastic, paint, etc.; with the means of connecting parts when cre-

ating a toy. Search work is initiated to identify toy characters or mosaic compositions.

Topic 2.4. – "Working with salt dough" – involves familiarizing older people with the composition of design of frames and various objects, design and decorative capabilities of salt dough. It includes questions such as preparation of materials to work; instruments and devices for making the compositions as well as details of decoration for designing frameworks and various items; color harmony, "unity of style".

Topic 2.5. – "creation of planar and three-dimensional compositions" – Artificial material (previously used materials: twine, buttons, beads, sequins, braid, mouline, etc.), its design capabilities. Feature and work with different materials. Safety and hygienic requirements in working with artificial material. Preparation of materials for the work. Ways to combine materials with each other (using glue, thread, wire). A technology of making products that contain different materials. Combination of ready-made forms without their change. Partial change of ready forms. Search for new technological and constructive solutions, ways of decorating products, conformity of the decor of the structure, artistic imagery, emotional expressiveness, color scheme.

Topic 2.6. – "Decoupage: planar and three-dimensional, design of vessels and glass and ceramic products; painting, decoration" – Features of work in the technique of decoupage, technology and materials. Search for new technological, constructive and compositional solutions, ways of decorating products, conformity of the decor of the structure, color tinting. Gradual execution of finishing products. Checkup of the work completion.

Topic 2.7. – " Application of fabric, ribbon, cotton twine, mouline thread " – Types of fabric, ribbon, twine, mouline thread and brief information about their production and application. Tools and accessories for working with fabric: scissors, needle, thimble, glue, pencils. Safety precautions. Preparation of materials for the work. Creating a composition. Color solution. Step-by-step execution of the application, additional finishing of a certain composition. Checkup of the work completion.

Topic 2.8. – "Fabric painting: batik, acrylic paints, pencil paints" – Technological sequence of batik (fabric painting). Techniques for painting fabrics. The invention of the expressiveness of the composition. Color solution of batik. Possibilities of acrylic paints. Use of pencils in the work.

Topic 2.9. – " Manufacture of dolls-motanka" – Technological sequence of execution of dolls-motanka, taking into account the design features of the toy and its proportions. Decorative design of the toy with a ribbon. Techniques of finishing. Expressiveness of the composition of the costume (silhouette, basic division, nature of the decor, color scheme, stylistic saturation, harmonious combination of elements of the ensemble).

To stimulate the creative process in the manufacture of fairy-tale characters, mastering a creative approach to making creative improvements, heuristic methods are used: "brainstorming" – generating ideas, "direct analogies" – transferring the characteristics of real objects to the created product, "fantastic" analogies, "combination", "improving", "presentation of ideas "and so on.

The expected short-term effects of assimilation rate was improving aesthetic and educational literacy and culture during the course of the pilot studies, developed by our training program, which is involved in all stages of preparation and certified by the relevant certificate of training.

At the same time, the entire project was designed for longer result – systematically in the organization of the rate of aesthetic and teacher education of the elderly as an important way of mitigating the problem of child abandonment in preschool children as a consequence of migration of parents. In addition, according to our plan, the appropriate education of the elderly was to initiate a chain reaction in society, increase pedagogical literacy and community culture on the basis of social responsibility for education of the younger generation of future citizens of Ukraine.

6. Conclusions

In general, the study provided the validity of the following conclusions:

1. Examining the state of labor migration in Ukraine, studying foreign and domestic experience in solving the problems of the elderly and the possibility of their involvement in education and work and post-work activities, including the arts, we can say that the elderly are an important labor resource for help. mitigation of the consequences of labor migration through strengthening the pedagogical potential of society in the direction of solving the problem of social orphanhood of preschool children.

The mission of the elderly on care for the younger generation, transmission of wisdom and social experience, preservation of Ukrainian national identity is one of natural and social endorsements in Ukrainian society classes for older people to keep, maintain and develop by encouraging seniors to the Ukrainian traditional type of labor activity, parenting, art classes, folk etc. This requires the development in society of various forms of non-formal adult education, which would expand the range of work skills throughout life through the implementation of mobile educational programs, aimed at providing older people with modern, relevant in society and, at the same time, natural and cultural work skills. Creative activity that involves direct communication with art, in addition, harmonizes the inner state of the elderly, promotes the level of his/her social health, encourages activity and creativity, learning and professional self-realization in the direction of creating an aesthetic and educational environment for future generations in Ukraine .

2. The results of a blitz survey, organized with students of preschool education in Kharkiv, confirmed the conclusions of scientists on the real state of the problem of pedagogical neglect and social orphanhood of preschool children in families, affected by labor migration, as well as the role of people of older age as potentially important to their subjects of pedagogical influence on children. Thus, it was found, that a large share of responsibility for the development and upbringing of children in this situation was taken by senior family members and / or elderly nannies, caregivers, governesses, who, at the same time, have some difficulty in caring for their children and pupils, first of all, the lack of pedagogical motivation, new methodical knowledge on the organization of educational activity with children, ability to

apply a creative approach to the development of the child's personality, etc.

3. Developed an educational project "Colourful world of childhood – experienced hands", aimed at developing older people, improving their ability to care for the youngest, giving them the ability to think, creativity, promoting skills in the fields of drawing, color, practical graphics, decorative arts and the basics of design, studying with them nature, the environment as an inexhaustible source of fine arts; contributing to the growth of the level of spirituality and the formation of aesthetic culture, the development of aesthetic and emotional attitude to works of decorative art and design, the ability to understand and appreciate folk art; education of an active attitude to the aesthetic phenomena of reality and art; purposeful and systematized formation of practical skills of artistic and creative activity.

The training program for older people to organize artistic and aesthetic activity of preschoolers is fully adapted to employment in the "University of the Third Age" or other similar structures of adult education and provides increasing the educational potential of older people, developing their ability to take care of the development of the individual of preschool age on the basis of the creative approach to education, imparting their skills in the field and art, developing the capability of art and one to understand and appreciate people's artistic creativity. The training course for students within this educational project consists of five modules: "Methods of teaching art to preschool children ", "Color", "Fundamentals of compositional literacy", "Drawing and open air workshop", "Decorative arts and design basics".

4. Within the course various types (drawing, artistic woodcarving, wickerwork, pottery, making a national toy, quilling, decorative painting, decoupage, making artificial flowers, embroidery, Easter painting) and forms (trainings, internships, practice, exchange of experience, conversation) of organization of art classes and pedagogical education of elderly people to prepare them for the care of preschool children, as well as training students to apply the acquired artistic and creative skills in the field of freelance and promotion of their own professional services were developed.

5. The project is designed for a long-term result - the systematic organization of a course of informal aesthetic and pedagogical education of the elderly as an important way to mitigate the problem of social orphanhood of preschool children as a result of labor migration of parents. Since the appropriate education of the elderly was to initiate a chain reaction in society, to ensure the increase of pedagogical literacy and community culture on the basis of social responsibility for education of the young generation of citizens of Ukraine

We plan to involve territorial service centers and public organizations in the implementation of the program of preparation of elderly people for the organization of artistic and aesthetic activities of preschoolers "Colourful world of childhood – experienced hands" as a platform for empowerment of the elderly to help them become leaders. Take an active part in the decision-making process at both local and regional levels. With the same purpose planned conducting interactive lessons and trips to art exhibitions of creative works of the elderly, etc.

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Received date 06.02.2020

Accepted date 22.06.2020

Published date 31.07.2020

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